

TITLE

The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Europe and Turkey: distribution map and GIS datasets

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DESCRIPTION

This work provides information on the species distribution of the *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Europe and Turkey. It includes unpublished geographical data that improves the information published to date on these species.

The GIS datasets correspond to 12 species of the *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Europe and Turkey. The ZIP file, "GIS datasets for the Rhyacophila Species Complex in Europe and Turkey.ZIP," includes shapefiles of points for the 12 species, available for free download. These shapefiles use WGS84 and include sampling locations, localities, countries, citation references, and, if available, DNA data. The attribute tables of the shapefiles are also available in Excel format as "Rhyacophila_Attribute Tables.xlsx". Complete References for the entries are in "Rhyacophila_References.pdf."

The Distribution map of the *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Europe and Turkey, over a digital elevation model (DEM) of Europe's land surface (Copernicus DEM of the Earth; GISCO, 2025), is available in PDF format.

FIVE FILES ARE INCLUDED:

- **Distribution map of the *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Europe and Turkey.pdf**
- **GIS datasets for the *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Europe and Turkey.ZIP**
- **Rhyacophila_Attribute Tables.xlsx**
- **Rhyacophila_References.pdf**
- **README.pdf**

Articles from which the GIS datasets of the *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex were extracted:

Valladolid, M., Arauzo, M., Basaguren, A., Dorda, B.A. & Rey, I. (2018) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Group in Western Europe: Confirmation of *Rhyacophila denticulata* McLachlan 1879 (stat. prom.) and *Rhyacophila sociata* Navás 1916 (stat. res.), based on morphological and molecular genetic evidence (Trichoptera: Rhyacophilidae), *Zootaxa*, 4418 (6), 526–544. <http://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4418.6.2>

Valladolid, M., Karaouzas, I., Arauzo, M., Dorda, B.A. & Rey, I. (2019) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Group in Greece: *Rhyacophila kykladica* Malicky & Sipahiler 1993 (stat. prom.) (Trichoptera: Rhyacophilidae). Morphological description, genetic and ecological features, *Zootaxa*, 4657 (3), 503–522. <http://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4657.3.5>

Valladolid, M., Kučinić, M., Arauzo, M., Cerjanec, D., Čuk, R., Dorda, B.A., Lodovici, O., Stanić Koštroman, S., Vučković, I. & Rey, I. (2020) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Group in Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina: *Rhyacophila f. fasciata* Hagen, 1859 and the description of two new subspecies, *Rhyacophila fasciata delici* Kučinić & Valladolid (ssp. nov.) from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina and *Rhyacophila fasciata viteceki* Valladolid & Kučinić (ssp. nov.) from Bosnia and Herzegovina (Trichoptera: Rhyacophilidae). *Zootaxa*, 4885 (1), 051–075. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4885.1.3>

Valladolid, M., Arauzo, M., Chertoprud, M., Chvojka, P., Czachorowski, S., Dorda, B.A, Hinić, J., Ibrahim, H., Karaouzas, I., Krpač, V., Kučinić, M., Lodovici, O., Salokannel, J., Slavevska Stamenković, V., Stojanović, K., Wallace, I. & Rey, I. (2021) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Group in Europe: *Rhyacophila fasciata* Hagen 1859 and formerly synonymized species (Trichoptera: Rhyacophilidae), with new description of *Rhyacophila fasciata*

and *Rhyacophila septentrionis* McLachlan 1865 (stat. prom.). *Zootaxa*, 4975 (1), 001–057. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4975.1.1>

Valladolid, M., Karaouzas, I., Ibrahimi, H., Arauzo, M., Slavevska Stamenković, V., Dorda, B.A., Hinić, J., Bilalli, A., Musliu, M. & Rey, I. (2022) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Group in Europe: *Rhyacophila macedonica* Karaouzas, Valladolid & Ibrahimi (n. sp.) from Greece, Kosovo, Republic of Macedonia and Serbia (Trichoptera: Rhyacophilidae). *Zootaxa*, 5125 (2), 101-130. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5125.2.1>

Valladolid, M., Waringer, J., Arauzo, M., Chvojka, P., Dorda, B. A., Komzák, P., Lodovici, O. & Rey, I. (2023) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Central Europe with description of a new species, *Rhyacophila loeffleri* Valladolid & Waringer, n. sp., based on morphological description, genetic and ecological evidence. *Zootaxa*, 5325 (4), 451–482. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5325.4.1>

Valladolid, M., Ekingen, P., Arauzo, M., Dorda, B.A. & Rey, I. (2024) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex in Turkey with description of a new species, *Rhyacophila anatolica* Ekingen & Valladolid, n. sp., based on morphological description genetic and ecological evidence. *Zootaxa*, 5537 (3), 301–324. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5537.3.1>

Valladolid, M., Arauzo, M., Coppa, G., Reding, J.-P. G., Dorda, B.A. & Rey, I. (2025) The *Rhyacophila fasciata* Species Complex (Trichoptera: Rhyacophilidae) in France and Switzerland, with description of a new species, *Rhyacophila caussensis* Valladolid & Coppa n. sp. from France, based on morphological, genetic and ecological evidence. *Zootaxa*, 5692 (3), 401-445. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5692.3.1>

Valladolid, M., Arauzo, M., Dorda, B.A., París, M. & Rey, I. (2025) Complete data of the DNA sequences used for the study of the *Rhyacophila fasciata* Group (Insecta, Trichoptera, Rhyacophilidae) in Europe. Dataset, Digital CSIC. Available from: <https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/260864>

References:

GISCO, 2025. Copernicus Digital Elevation Model. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/digital-elevation-model/copernicus#Elevation>. (accessed 2 October 2025)